

Cadmium (II), Mercury (II), Lead (II) and Cobalt (II) Chelates of 5-sulpho- β -resorcylic acid and Stability constants of the Complexes

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IN the present work the stability constants of some divalent metal complexes, formed by 5-sulpho- β -resorcylic acid (Abbr-SBRA) have been studied by Bjerrum-Calvin pH titration technique^{1,2} as used by Irving and Rossotti³. The stepwise proton-ligand stability constant of ligand and stability constants of the divalent metal complexes were determined. The metal ions used are mercury (II), lead (II), cobalt (II) and cadmium (II). These metals have been found to form solid complexes with SBRA. From the values of stability constants of the metal chelates the order is Hg, Pb, Co, Cd. This order of stabilities is the same as found by Irving-William⁴ for divalent metal complexes.

The curve obtained for proton-ligand system was of inverted 'S' shape extending between $\bar{n}A = 0.27$ and $\bar{n}A = 0.95$ showing that, only one proton is dissociated from the phenolic group ortho to carboxylic group as is found with the parent compound β -resorcylic acid⁵⁻⁷. The values of stability constants were read off directly from the formation curves (Figs. 1 and 2) at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and $\bar{n} = 1.5$. The results are given as follows :

VALUES OF STABILITY CONSTANTS OF METAL CHELATES

(Ionic strength 0.1M)

Sl.No.	Metal	Interpolation at half n values	successive appo. method	Mean
1.	Hg(II) log K_1 log K_2	6.50 5.05	6.4512 5.0988	6.4756 5.0744
2.	Pb(II) log K_1 log K_2	5.40 4.70	not applicable	5.40 4.20
3.	Co(II) log K_1	4.00	—	4.00
4.	Cd(II) log K_1	3.50	—	3.50

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Determination of Mercaptans with Halogen Cyanides at Elevated Temperatures

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IODINE and bromine cyanides have recently been utilised as volumetric oxidants in these laboratories¹⁻⁵ and have been found to react with mercaptans in the molar ratio 1 : 2 at room temperature⁶. An attempt has now been made to study the reaction at elevated temperatures.

Experimental

Reagents and Solutions : Iodine cyanide, bromine cyanide and the mercaptans were prepared and/or purified according to the procedures referred to earlier⁶. Solutions (0.01M) of halogen cyanides were prepared in 0.1M hydrochloric acid and those of the mercaptans (0.01M) in double distilled water except for thio-*p*-cresol and propyl mercaptan which were dissolved in minimum ethanol and then diluted with water.

Titrimetric procedure : An aliquot of the solution of the mercaptan (1-3 ml) was added to that of the halogen cyanide (5-10 ml) taken in excess. The contents were heated at different temperature ranges such as 40°-50°, 50°-60°, 60°-70°, 70°-80° and 80°-90° for different time intervals using water condenser and then cooled to room temperature. The unconsumed halogen cyanide was titrated with aqueous sodium thiosulphate solution (0.01M) using starch indicator. Potassium iodide (5-10 ml, 10 per cent solution), was added in the titrations with bromine cyanide.

Results and Discussion

It is inferred from the present study that the extent of oxidation of mercaptans with iodine cyanide or bromine cyanide is a direct function of time and temperature. The conditions for 1 : 1 molar ratio of the mercaptan and halogen cyanide are cited in Table 1. No experiment corresponded to any other stoichiometry. Since thioacetic acid is decomposed on heating in the presence of dilute hydrochloric acid⁷, the reaction is carried out at room temperature (25°-30°). However, stoichiometric results could not be obtained in case of thiomalic acid even by varying the experimental conditions appreciably. The